

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and **blue economy**

Deliverable D3.4 - Gap analysis for VA

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- **Executive Summary**

An analysis of the virtual services offered in the AQUASERV project was carried out. Three partners – Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI), and the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) – offer access to several of their databases via machine-focused web tools (e.g. API) and human-focused web interfaces (e.g. information search interfaces). These services were tested with an eye on inspecting their findability from their home page, understandability via the interface layout and documentation, and the interoperability and reusability of the outputs (the I and R of the FAIR data principles). Almost all the tested services – the human and the machine-focused – were easy to find and use, with clearly presented purpose and a variety of useful output formats. However, for almost all the services, the documentation could be improved by being clearer, more comprehensive, and with more examples. Additionally, the interoperability of the outputs for some services could be improved.

A handful of e-services are also offered in AQUASERV via the ARIA platform in the context of transnational access. For a number of reasons, these services could not be tested for this deliverable; however, analysis of these may be taken up later in the project, together with WP7 (which manages the TA programme).

1. Introduction

1.1. The AQUASERV project

AQUASERV – RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE, FISHERIES AND THE BLUE ECONOMY

The AQUASERV project is a five-year initiative, running from April 2024 to March 2029, funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide research services that support sustainable aquaculture, fisheries, and the blue economy. AQUASERV involves collaboration among 40 partners across Europe and is aligned with the goals of the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 call, which focuses on RI services to enable research and innovation (R&I) to address key challenges and EU priorities.

The overarching objectives of AQUASERV are to enhance, integrate, and customise research infrastructures (RI) capacities (including facilities, instruments, and expertise) and through the provision of transnational access (on-site or remote) and virtual access, to significantly further scientific knowledge and promote and facilitate the implementation of European Common Fisheries Policy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, the Sustainable Blue Economy, and the [European Green Deal](#).

AQUASERV will achieve these objectives by offering scientists from academia and industry remote and on-site transnational (TA) and virtual (VA) access to services from an advanced set of European RIs related to research and management of marine and freshwater biological resources, food, and biotechnology. These RIs include The International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC), Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems (AnaEE-ERIC), AQUAEXCEL, and Infrastructure for Promoting Metrology in Food and Nutrition (METROFOOD-RI). AQUASERV also includes the RI for European Research Infrastructure for Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS) to garner contributions from the social sciences and aid the translation of results to policymakers, thereby enhancing the societal impact of the project.

1.2. The AQUASERV Virtual Services

The virtual services of AQUASERV are provided by three organisations: Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), and the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI). Virtual services in AQUASERV are e-services that are accessible via a web browser and which can be used without needing to contact the service provider for help, instructions, or installation. The services offered by these three organisations are listed in Table 1; they are all some variant of marine

data-providing service, focused on humans (scientists and other data consumers) and machines (developers, automated processes). All 32 services were analysed for this report.

1.3. The AQUASERV e-Services

In addition to these virtual services, several AQUASERV partners provide services that are categorised as “e-services” in the ARIA catalogue. These services are listed in Table 2; the services offered range from bioinformatics, datasets, spatial planning, to system biology modelling. Nine e-services (i.e. bioinformatics at CSIS, IFREMER, JU, SZN, UNITO-Aqua, UNITO-Insects, ECIMAT-UVIGO, datasets at JSI, and system biology monitoring at ECIMAT-UVIGO) are categorised as off-site services. However, most of these services are not virtual services in the sense that they are not accessible via a URL typed into a web browser, but rather are onsite, or remote use of services that are onsite, e-platforms (e.g. bioinformatics), code to be downloaded and installed, e-tools as part of lab systems, etc. Due to this, it was decided not to evaluate these systems for this report, but to consider them later, together with WP7, within the context of their being ARIA TA services.

2. The Landscaping

2.1. Scope and methodology

To landscape the virtual services, we asked each of the three providers for the URLs of the home page of their services and the direct URLs for each service. We gathered administrative information for each service – these are given in Table 1 – and tested each service following a [template report](#)¹. The aim was to test the usability and user-friendliness of the services and the FAIRness of their outputs; we did not test the validity or accuracy of the services, this being beyond the scope of this deliverable. The template report requires the tester to: assume a user-type (e.g. “a scientist looking for information relevant to their research”), check if the service can be found from the institute’s home page, report on the user-friendliness of the service interface and the quality of the documentation, provide some examples of inputs and outputs, and to suggest any additions to the services. Where outputs were produced (other than just a single value), the tester was asked to check the FAIRness of those outputs with a focus on their interoperability (e.g. use of semantics to make data globally understandable) and reusability (provision of information about how the results were computed/extracted).

¹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1U7mhUYi_EuNoPZXg73RlyyFJJSH-d67ZprpOFFEaQqWA/edit?usp=drive_link

The individual reports can be found in our Google Drive: for [VLIZ](#)², for [ICES](#)³, for [JSI](#)⁴. These reports are summarised next.

2.2. Results

Here we present the key findings of the landscaping of each group of services, including their strong points and suggestions for improvements.

■ 2.2.1 Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)

VLIZ provides numerous endpoints for services working from: the Marine Regions Gazetteer, the Marine Species database, and the EurOBIS database.

Marine Regions

Seven services were tested: querying the gazetteer for marine region information via a web interface and via its REST and SOAP APIs, querying EEZ (European Exclusive Economic Zones) and other marine zone data, various web services, and some mapping services. These are listed in Table 1.

Gazetteer One can browse and search on the gazetteer, to find the IDs, names, coordinates, or maps of regions in the Marine Regions database: you can browse on an HTML page with a clickable (open/close) list from which you can browse regions and subregions; and you can search via a web form from which you can search on Marine Region ID (MRGID), name, or coordinates to obtain a list of regions. In both, one can then click on a region to get to the web page for that region, in which coordinates, names, sources, and maps are provided.

Positives: For these two services, the interfaces are self-explanatory and easy to use. The results pages are also easy to understand. For any particular region, a navigable map is provided on its web page, and for regions with defined borders (e.g. countries, oceans), different versions of a map can be downloaded, including in the JSON-LD format (making the results machine-usable).

Suggestions for improvement For the search, (i) one cannot save the results into a file (e.g. CSV, JSON-LD formats), (ii) not all the input boxes on the search interface are explained (e.g. what are the units of the

² https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/14dYzGkQDegLXdyfWK9whbWpmar-aqNoW?usp=drive_link

³ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ogLZ6Mse1zeSzuSG1Fw532dfVomMcu_g?usp=drive_link

⁴ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1HKPoGQnYBVYN3C3SGNQ9j3xKD3odCizj?usp=drive_link

radius?), (iii) the results contain some unexplained acronyms (e.g. “TWDG - level 3” when searching on “Belgium”), (iv) when you enter a large radius, a very long list of resulting matches is returned and this is difficult to navigate – providing a map-based tool for defining a search area would be useful. For the web page for any particular marine region (e.g. for [Belgium](#)), while it is nice that an interactive map is provided, it has a somewhat faded colour scheme that makes details hard to see. For some regions around the poles (more north than south), the map also looks distorted (e.g. see the [Agafonov Seamount](#)) to the human eye: this is because of the projection used, and while a sphere on a flat surface will never be right, nonetheless, it is difficult for the non-geographically-aware person to appreciate. Note that one cannot download a copy of this map, and the versions that can be downloaded from the specific function only show the borders of the region, and not any underlying or outlying geography.

Gazetteer web services. The services are divided into RESTful and SOAP-based APIs, with additional support for OGC services, an R package using those services, GeorSS feeds, and Linked Data Event Streams (LDES).

Positives: These are substantial machine-focused additions to the human-focused services. The REST services available are each listed on a dedicated web page, one can try them out there, and the results include the necessary request URL and Curl command string to run them yourself (handy for beginner developers). The GeorSS and LDES feeds are for experts to use rather than the average scientist, but they are extremely useful for making the Marine Region information machine-accessible and interoperable, allowing these data to be incorporated in anyone else’s web pages and web services. An R package is provided that demonstrates how to use the services in R (a commonly-used coding language by the user base).

Suggestions for improvements REST (i) the terms used in the results should be explained (e.g. what is “precision”, what is “SAIL” as a “gazetteerSource”), (ii) most of the calls provide results in JSON and XML, some also in JSON-LD – more of the latter would be more machine-friendly. SOAP services: (i) the web page for these services is rather minimal with a hard to read colour scheme: we suggest the provision of the same documentation approach (swagger) used for the REST services, (iii) there is an R package that uses the Marine Regions web services, it would be useful to provide examples in python as well, as this is a commonly-used language for developers. REST and SOAP (i) output of the APIs in JSON-LD with the schema response explained in swagger would make these outputs more interoperable and usable, (ii) the query URL and input parameters should be included in the response for greater reusability of the output data. GeorSS (i) the GeorSS feed could be enhanced with more information for better

understandability (if possible). LDES feed: (i) There is limited documentation available on the service description page. Additional guidance on how to use the LDES feed effectively would be beneficial, including examples of how to consume the LDES feed and integrate it with other systems.

Maritime Boundaries The search on the maritime boundaries is to query (by name or coordinates) a fixed list of marine boundaries – EEZs, the Territorial Seas, Internal Waters, and Contiguous Zones – to access the geographical information about them. This can be done via a web form (search) and map (mapper).

Positives: The map provided on any boundary page contains a wealth of information that is well-presented, well-documented, and a GML (geographic markup) version is also provided for machine usability.

Suggestions for improvements (i) While the [documentation page](#)⁵ explains where the different zones come from, some more information could be provided rather than expecting the user to click through the UNICLOS website. (ii) The documentation could be better presented, as there is a lot of information and flashing images to get through. (iii) Additional documentation⁶ is nicely written, but it is unclear to what results they refer: better links between the various documentation pages should be provided. (v) It would be useful to provide the maps not only in GML but also in GeoJSON and RDF. (iv) There does not appear to be any web service provided to perform the same queries by developers (e.g. no APIs): if this is the case, it would be extremely useful to add and document these, and to provide examples of how to integrate them into external applications.

Maps: This repository contains static maps (World maps, North Sea maps, Europe, etc.) for various maritime regions, allowing users to browse, search, and download maps for research, education, and policy-making purposes.

Positives: The platform uses a web-based interface with a photo gallery layout. It includes thumbnails for easy navigation and categorisation of maps into albums. The interface is intuitive, with basic search functionality and options to download static maps.

Suggestions for improvements (i) While the interface is user-friendly, additional documentation on map usage, metadata, and licensing would enhance the user experience, (ii) more standardised metadata

⁵ <https://www.marineregions.org/eezmethodology.php>

⁶ <https://www.marineregions.org/eezattribute.php>, <https://www.marineregions.org/eezlinetype.php>

(licence, provenance) for each map would enhance their FAIRness, (iii) more search filters could be added (a string search is offered)

Marine Species / WoRMS

For Marine Species, also known as the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), there are web services (REST and SOAP) and web-based portals to access the Aphia database behind WoRMS. Part of WoRMS is WRIMS – World Register of Invasive Marine Species – and this also has web services and web portals.

Suggestions for improvements: The WRIMS website is not separate but rather a page on WoRMS. Nonetheless, it is presented to users as if it is a separate website, and if that is a choice, then (i) WRIMS should be linked to WoRMS, and vice versa, from their home pages, (ii) the WRIMS web “site” has an old-fashioned appearance, and we suggest an update, e.g. to match the WoRMS look-and-feel.

Web Services Both WoRMS and WRIMS have REST and SOAP services to access their data, and they are both effectively the same since WRIMS is just a subset of the WoRMS database.

Positives: These services provide machine-accessibility to valuable taxonomic information for developers, which can then be used in other services, portals, databases, and codes. The services are easy to find from the home page, having their own dedicated web pages in which each call is outlined – that for the REST services (swagger) is particularly nicely and usefully laid out. The REST services are also described in a YAML file, and the SOAP services in a WSDL⁷ (XML) file. The services provide numerous examples provided in R, Perl, Python, etc.

Suggestions for improvements: The presentation of the REST and SOAP calls, and their documentation, is the same as those for Marine Regions, and the same comments apply, therefore. (i) The SOAP services description page is rather minimal and difficult to read (especially for those with some eyesight issues), and lacks examples, (ii) the REST services descriptions are incomplete as there are input parameters for some calls that are not explained: for example, AphiaAttributeKeysByID requires an “attribute definition ID” as input, but there is no information about what these attributes are and what the range of IDs are. There is a YAML file provided via the web page that describes the services, but these information are not provided there either, (iii) it would be useful to provide REST examples in python as well as R, as this is more commonly used by developers (as opposed to marine scientists), (iv) input and output of the APIs (REST and SOAP) should be defined in JSON-LD (and also explained in plain text); with the schema

⁷ Web Services Description Language

response explained in swagger the outputs from these web services would be more interoperable and usable, (v) the query URL and input parameters should be included in the response for greater reusability of the output data. Finally, these web services are not findable from the WRIMS website; a menu item for this needs to be added.

Web Portals Two types of services are offered here: WoRMS and WRIMS offer a taxon match tool, and WoRMS offers a taxon browser. The first allows one to upload a spreadsheet with species names in it, to get back that spreadsheet with information taken from the database added. The second provides a web page with an expandable list of the taxonomic names, i.e. the taxonomic classifications.

Positives: The browse service is self-explanatory – one simply click-navigates through the classification “trees”. The taxon match service provides a very useful way for scientists to collect information from WoRMS for their recorded marine organisms, e.g. to add PIDs (the so-called AphiaIDs) to species names in their published data and so increasing its interoperability (e.g. this is a requirement for data submitted to OBIS). The web form is easy to use. The outputs are interoperable: not only is the AphiaID given as an integer, but its related LSID is also given.

Suggestions for improvements: For the taxon browse service (i) it would be useful be able to access this as linked data (as is the case for Marine Regions and its LDES feed), to make that machine usable (note that this is currently under development in the MareGraph project, we suggest that there is a link made to the eventual project to this WoRMS website). For the taxon match service, (i) better documentation of what information added to your input spreadsheet from WoRMS or WRIMS would make the service more user-friendly and understandable: currently one has to understand what the information is just from its title (“ScientificName”, “TSN”), (ii) one minor issue with the form: it loses the chosen input file if you click to go “back” a page, (iii) output in CSV should be offered, as well as the text, Excel, and SGML (XML), (iv) as well as including the LSID in the output, we would suggest adding the aphiaID as a URL (e.g. <https://aphia.org/id/taxname/508515>) but we note here that in fact this is ongoing work in the MareGraph project, (v) one final minor interoperability point: some null values are given as “null” in the output and others as a blank cell: either use one or the other.

EurOBIS / EMODnet

EurOBIS (European Ocean Biodiversity Information System) is a node of OBIS (Ocean Biodiversity Information System) and provides data on occurrences and related measurements from the oceans around Europe or from European-based researchers.. It is closely linked with EMODnet Biology (European

Marine Observation and Data Network) and provides that portal with its biology data (EMODnet also collects data on bathymetry, human activities, physics, chemistry, ...). EurOBIS's focus is on collecting and publishing data, and most of the services for accessing those data are provided via EMODnet: it is these services (those providing biological data, excluding the services primarily for physics, chemistry, etc) that we tested here. Note that EMODnet is not a VLIZ service, so any recommendations made here will have to be sent to them separately.

These services are: the EMODnet portal, which provides a web-based map tool to search, select, and display EMODnet datasets, and one can also browse its product catalogue; web services (OGC, WFS, WMS, ERDDAP, and a few others).

EMODnet portal: map viewer and product catalogue. The portal provides a map-based search and view and the product catalogue. These services are focused on the human user. The product catalogue offers a few filters to search on, primarily a (broad) resource type, a (broad) data topic, and a search string. When clicking to search on a resource type, a new interface is presented, which offers more search filters based on ranges of location, dates, providers, keywords, and other criteria. The map viewer allows one to select what type of data to display in different layers.

Positives: The product catalogue offers multiple languages for the search, for which EMODnet should be congratulated. The range of search filters offered on the more advanced search page is comprehensive. The map viewer is a convenient way to view the data available from all the EMODnet catalogues. While the documentation and viewer themselves could use some improvements, they work well once one understands how to use them.

Suggestions for improvement: For the product catalogue, (i) the more useful filter-search interface seems to be accessible only when one clicks to search on a resource type - it is not accessible from the [product catalogue home page](#)⁸. It would be more user-friendly if this [advanced search](#)⁹ were the first one encountered by users, being the more useful version. For the map viewer, (i) it takes some time to figure out how to use it, e.g. being presented with an empty "Layer" tab in the initial view, it is not intuitive that one needs to first select from the "Catalogue" tab (which is positioned below the "Layer" tab) to see any Layers. Using pop-ups to explain to the user what to do would help, as well as having the "Catalogue" being the upper tab in the first view on the page, (ii) the [documentation](#)¹⁰ provided could use more screenshots (rather than saying e.g. "...the legend in the second button to the left"), it could also use a

⁸ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/cat/catalog.search#/home>

⁹ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search>

¹⁰ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/faq-about-downloading-emodnet-data>

little editing (some spell-checking; numbered lists to match highlighted numbers in the screenshots, rather than bulleted lists; and some of the screenshots need updating as the current mapper has differences), (iii) when following the instructions to select data from biodiversity datasets, clicking on the funnel symbol next to the “Biodiversity records”, the popup “Biodiversity records” allowing “Access to metadata” sends you to a page with metadata on EurOBIS, rather than metadata for the data you have just highlighted: this is user-unfriendly as it is not what one would expect; in addition, the Download from that popup gives you a parquet file, which not everyone will know how to open (adding this to the documentation would be useful) (iv) when selecting from the Catalogue and displaying on the map, it can take a long time (>1minute(s)) to load where there is much data (and one cannot stop it): where this is a lot of data this is understandable, but nonetheless it is frustrating for the user. Other functions are also rather slow, again understandable but frustrating.

EMODnet web services For the biological data of EMODnet, there are OGC¹¹ web services in R, a CSW¹² endpoint of the catalogue, WMS¹³, WMTS¹⁴, WCS¹⁵, and WFS¹⁶ services, REST APIs, and an ERDDAP service. These provide access to EMODnet data for developers and machines.

The ERDDAP service, which is a REST-like service supporting queries in CSV, JSON, NetCDF to find and download EMODnet data in their various formats. It is aimed at developers, data scientists, and modellers. ERDDAP provides built-in human- and machine-readable documentation. *Suggestions for improvements*: although there were many output formats offered, linked data was not one of them, limiting machine-based interoperability. One can browse a full list of datasets available for download, and browse subsets of the full list based on category selections. An improvement on this interface is suggested. For example, to categorise on “keywords”, one is presented with a list of every single keyword in the database: given that many of these are free-text strings that the data providers added, this list is very long and hence difficult to navigate; in addition, only single keywords are selectable at a time.

The various web-XXX services (WMS, WMTS, WCS, and WFS) provide geospatial information, maps, tiles, etc., via a simple HTTP interface, and support several operations as defined by the OGS standard. Three endpoints for EMODnet biology are provided: data products, new data products (but not for WFS and WCS), and occurrence data. The documentation for the endpoints was easy to find and sufficient to get

¹¹ Open Geospatial Consortium

¹² Catalogue Services for the Web

¹³ Web Map Service

¹⁴ Web Map Tile Service

¹⁵ Web Coverage Service

¹⁶ Web Feature Service

started with the calls. *Suggestions for improvements* (i) Additional examples to demonstrate integration of the service into code/a web page are recommended. These services are for developers, not casual scientists; as such its documentation in XML is acceptable, although it is always better to also have documentation written into a web page (HTML), to accommodate a wider audience. Some improvements in the presentation of the documentation are suggested: all the documentation is provided on the same “Data visualisation services” web page, making it rather crowded. (ii) There is only a little documentation provided to explain the returned values of the calls (in particular, GetCapabilities). (iii) The returned values themselves are in txt/xml, which are poorly formatted in a standard web browser (and so difficult to read).

The R tutorial for EMODnet OGC webservices provides tutorials for accessing EMODnet data directly in R using OGC Web Services. It is designed for researchers, data analysts, and developers who work with marine geospatial data. The tutorial provides all necessary code and examples, and took about 30 mins to work through (for someone already familiar with R). The tutorial is hosted on GitHub and provides clear instructions, including links to Jupyter Notebooks for interactive learning. *Suggestions for improvement:* (i) provide more examples specific to EuroBIS web services, (ii) include a troubleshooting section for common issues encountered while using the services, (iii) offer downloadable datasets for offline practice.

The CSW endpoint to the EMODnet central catalogue provides a standard CSW interface, which is widely recognised and supported by various GIS tools and libraries. The documentation is comprehensive, detailing the available operations, parameters, and example queries. It includes examples for GetCapabilities, GetRecords, and GetRecordById operations. *Suggestions for Improvement:* (i) The documentation could benefit from more troubleshooting tips and a quick-start guide, including more real-world query examples, such as filtering metadata records by keywords or retrieving specific datasets, and adding a troubleshooting section for common issues.

EuroBIS data catalogue and data download service. EuroBIS offers a data catalogue browse service and a data download web interface. The data catalogue searches the EuroBIS datasets, which are stored in IMIS (the Integrated Marine Information System, also now known as [MarineInfo](https://marineinfo.org/)¹⁷). The data download HTML interface allows users to select data that fits within a geographic area, time frame, and is based on the source of the data (country, origin of data, etc.).

¹⁷ <https://marineinfo.org/>

Positives: The data catalogue has a good number of filters to search datasets, and a fair number of those offer drop-downs to select from. The search results are for the metadata records for those datasets, from which the data can be downloaded. The search results are grouped by parent records, as much of the data in EurOBIS has a parent-child relationship: this is very useful. The service is focused on humans; however, the metadata can also be downloaded in various machine-friendly formats (EML, JSON-LD, INSPIRE-XML, etc.). The data download interface is intuitive to use and is particularly useful because it allows you to save the URL that will allow that same set of filters to be run again. This enhances the reusability of the search action and its resulting data.

Suggestions for improvements For the data search (i) On the search form, the “Thesaurus term” field can be selected from a list or entered as a string: from personal knowledge we are aware that many data providers added their keywords as strings, rather than from such lists: we hope that the search in this field works with fuzzy matches on strings entered there. (ii) It is difficult to know *a priori* what to enter in the “Parameter” field in the search form, since there is no information given about how parameters are named in the database and what the “parameter” should be (e.g. chemical measurements, taxonomic groups?). (iii) One cannot save the list of search results to a file. (iv) Once one has chosen a dataset and been directed to its metadata catalogue page, the metadata are displayed (HTML). Although several other versions of the metadata are available (XML, EML, JSON-LD), this is not advertised on that dataset metadata page. (v) For the [one metadata record we inspected](#), while contact names are given, contact IDs (e.g. ORCID) or email addresses are not given. (vi) The keywords list for that one record is very long, as it includes the geographic and species information, which are anyway listed elsewhere in the record: this has the effect of hiding the actual keywords added by the data provider. (vii) To provide the full functionality of this service for machines (developers) to use would be extremely useful. For the data download, (a) while the interface is intuitive to use, and there are information buttons (e.g. taking you to the metadata catalogue page for listed datasets), nonetheless some usage documentation would be useful (for example, at the end one is offered the data to download in different formats, but no explanation of those formats and what they do/do not include is provided), (b) the interface could benefit from the inclusion of linked data to enhance integration capabilities with other systems to provide the full functionality of this service for machines (developers) to use would be extremely useful.

Marine Info and the Integrated Marine Information System

VLIZ has a catalogue system for datasets, people, organisations, and more. IMIS (the Integrated Marine Information System) is the database, and the public face of that is on the [Marine Info](https://marineinfo.org)¹⁸ website. Using the catalogue is open to everyone and provides access to metadata records from which linked datasets or publications can be downloaded. It is also possible to submit datasets to be published by filling out a metadata form and uploading or providing access to the related dataset(s).

Metadata catalogue search, view, and download. We concentrated on the catalogues for datasets and publications. The search interface on Marine Info allows for a wide range of filters to be set. The service offers a human interface to the catalogue (<https://marineinfo.org/search>) and provides machine access to the metadata (<https://marineinfo.org/products-and-services>).

Positives: The search interface is nice and intuitive to use, with a wide range of filters adjusted according to the “documentation type” (e.g. dataset or publication) you are looking for. The list of results is easy to read. The web page of a metadata record contains abundant information, and links to the contacts (to the people catalogue), to species names (in WoRMS), and to locations (in Marine Regions) are given. The possibility to directly access different machine-readable and understandable versions of the metadata (XML, EML, JSON, JSON-LD) is very welcome.

Suggestions for improvements (i) The options in the geographic filter are (presumably) based on what is in the data, but do have limitations (e.g. I cannot search a specific *part* of the Atlantic): we suggest a latitude-longitude filter (via boxes and via a map) be added. (ii) For the taxonomic search, again, what is offered is presumably what is recorded in the data, but it appears to be limited to 20 names. We suggest that a specific search on taxonomic classification (name and rank) be added, perhaps by linking to the WoRMS database. (iii) There is no way to save the list of results to a file; we suggest this is added, allowing for a range of (human- and machine-focused) formats. (iv) For the web page that is any one metadata record, we suggest that the font is increased, as currently it is unfriendly to those with sight issues. (v) The metadata record cannot be saved to a file; we suggest that this be made possible (in all the formats that are offered). (v) While some of the tested search engines produced a link to IMIS, someone who did not know what “IMIS” was would miss that; in addition, IMIS is almost invisible on the VLIZ home page. It is easier to find on the MarineInfo web page (as “Search”), but that MarineInfo page is poorly linked from the VLIZ page and rather invisible on the web to searches on “data catalogue / publishing”. Finally, (vi) we suggest that a button be added to the human interface to the catalogue

¹⁸ <https://marineinfo.org/search>

records to allow them to export the metadata in the various formats offered via <https://marineinfo.org/products-and-services>.

Metadata submission: One can fill in a metadata form to publish a dataset. It is possible to attach the data to the form, to upload it to the Marine Data Archive (see below), or to make it available for the IMIS team to access. The metadata are reviewed, and after passing, the metadata are added to IMIS and made findable on MarineInfo.

Positives: The metadata form is intuitive to fill in, and additionally provides information about what fields satisfy the FAIR data publication principles. The embedded help is generally well written.

Suggestions for improvements (i) To add a field for the ORCIDs of all people entered in the record (contact, creator, etc). (ii) Linking the measurements to suitable vocabularies (e.g. those of BODC) would make the metadata more interoperable. Finally, (iii) while some of the tested search engines produced a link to IMIS, someone who did not know what “IMIS” was would miss that; in addition, using IMIS to publish data, and IMIS in and of itself, is almost invisible on the VLIZ home page and is also not immediately obvious on the MarineInfo page (it is there under “Submit” (“submit *what?*”). That MarineInfo page is poorly linked from the VLIZ page and at the present time rather invisible on the web to searches on “data catalogue / publishing”.

Marine Data Archive

The Marine Data Archive (MDA) is a VLIZ service for archiving and sharing data. It archives data that can be linked to the IMIS database and hence dataset metadata records in MarineInfo, but it can also be used to share data among projects or to make them available for referees reviewing a submitted scientific paper.

Positives: The home page is straightforward and nicely uncluttered. The archive itself is a file server, and the overall look and feel is intuitive. The documentation is nicely written, with good use of screenshots to complement the text. That this service is provided free of charge is generous.

Suggestions for improvements (i) The home page of MDA could use a modernisation. (ii) There is no way to see a link between a file in the MDA and the MarineInfo metadata record it is associated with: it would improve the user-friendliness of both these services for those users who are themselves storing data in the MDA to make accessible via MarineInfo. (iii) We suggest adding a diagram of the workflow to be followed to upload and archive a file or a series of files in the MDA. (iv) The metadata form in the MDA is

unrelated to the metadata form for IMIS/MarineInfo, and this seems to be an own goal, especially as the MDA metadata form does not allow for any use of vocabularies and does not include the same FAIR-friendly range of fields as the IMIS/MarineInfo one. Finally, (v) while all tested search engines produced the direct link to the MDA, it is almost invisible on the VLIZ home page, and very hard to find on the MarineInfo web page.

■ 2.2.2 International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)

The nine services tested for ICES (Table 1) are APIs (SOAP and REST) for accessing data held in various databases at ICES, and a search interface to the ICES metadata catalogue.

REST API for stock assessment data

This provides programmatic access to ICES stock metadata through several protocols – RESTful API, OData V3 and V4 services – of which the REST services were tested here. Developers wanting to integrate stock assessment data into applications will find these services useful. The audience expected is marine scientists, fisheries researchers, and policy advisers.

Positives: For developers used to APIs, the interface is relatively straightforward. There is documentation for each API. Detailed instructions for using the APIs with R (via the GitHub repository and presentation) are available. The services are documented with technical descriptions and example R code, aiding machine-to-machine interactions.

Suggestions for improvements: (i) The documentation is not friendly to novice users, and lacks step-by-step example use cases, (ii) based on the documentation and user interface, it is clear that the service provides access to meta-information about ICES stocks. However, the steps required to utilise the service are not immediately obvious, and users may need to refer to multiple documents to understand the process fully. (iii) a fully machine-readable API specification (e.g. OpenAPI) is not available, and further details on input parameters and expected outputs could be expanded, (iv) the outputs should be provided in RDF with semantic annotation to allow full understandability of all the terms and values.

SOAP API for Eggs and Larvae data

Provides programmatic access to data on fish eggs and larvae, including haul metadata and measurement records. The service is aimed at marine scientists, fisheries researchers, and biodiversity scientists.

Positives: For developers used to APIs, the interface is relatively straightforward. There is documentation for each API. Detailed instructions for using the APIs with R (via the GitHub repository and presentation) are available.

Suggestions for improvements: To improve FAIRness, services could include richer metadata, clearer documentation, persistent identifiers, use of standard vocabularies, dataset versioning, and more machine-actionable outputs with practical examples. The data outputs are structured in a consistent format, promoting interoperability. Built on RESTful principles, the APIs leverage standard HTTP status codes, making them easily interoperable with various tools and libraries.

More specifically: (i) For novice users, the interface presents a learning curve. Improved documentation, including step-by-step tutorials and practical sample requests and responses in the documentation, would enhance clarity and user confidence. Providing sample requests and responses would improve the comprehensiveness of the documentation, (ii) machine-readable documentation (e.g., OpenAPI specifications) should be provided, (iii) the outputs should be provided in RDF with semantic annotation to allow full understandability of all the terms and values (e.g. “species” is taken from which taxonomic backbone – this should be given as a WoRMS ID, for example; what is “stage” LV?).

SOAP API for DATRAS data on trawl surveys

Provides programmatic access to trawl survey data, including haul-based, length-based, and age-based information. The service is aimed at marine scientists, fisheries researchers, and bioinformaticians who require programmatic access to trawl survey datasets.

Positives: For individuals with experience in web services and API consumption, the interface is relatively straightforward. The service's documentation provides descriptions of each API, including input parameters and expected outputs. The services are documented with a Web Service Description Language (WSDL) document, which can be used to create clients that access the service. This facilitates machine-to-machine interactions by providing a standard method for describing the web service's functionalities.

Suggestions for improvements (i) For novice users, the interface may present a learning curve. Understanding how to construct requests and handle responses requires familiarity with web service protocols. It took approximately two hours to become proficient in using the service, including time spent reviewing the documentation and testing various endpoints. Improved documentation, including step-by-step tutorials and practical sample requests and responses in the documentation, would enhance clarity and user confidence. Providing sample requests and responses would improve the comprehensiveness of the documentation. (ii) The outputs should be provided in RDF with semantic annotation to allow full understandability of all the terms and values.

VME REST API

This service provides programmatic access to Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) records, including species, habitat type, status, spatial information, and survey metadata. The endpoint `/GetPublicRecordsVMEDataSet` returns JSON objects with detailed metadata per observation taken from the VME database.

Positives: The output of the API is in JSON format, which is machine-readable. The API offers access to a lot of useful information.

Suggestions for improvements: The DATRAS web services already provide open, stable, and taxonomically linked data, which supports FAIRness. To further align with FAIR, the services should enrich metadata, expose data in multiple machine-actionable formats, harmonise field codes with controlled vocabularies, and add clear documentation and licensing.

More specifically: (i) A suggestion to move from JSON to JSON-LD, so the outputs are not only machine-readable but also machine-understandable with a defined schema and the use of semantics for better interoperability. (ii) Some understanding of VME datasets is required to use the service – users may need to cross-reference species, habitat, and survey metadata externally. To counter this, the documentation should be improved, for example, by defining the fields, valid ranges, and units; including example queries and responses; and clarifying any internal or temporary records flagged in the database. (iii) Add licence and version information to support reusability.

Acoustic web service

The ICES Acoustic Web Service exposes endpoints to query acoustic survey datasets maintained by ICES programmatically. The service enables the retrieval of survey data for research, ecosystem monitoring,

and fisheries assessment. The service is primarily intended for marine scientists, fisheries researchers, and data engineers

Positives: The service lists all API endpoints via Swagger, allowing machine-readable inspection. The interface is easy to use and understand for developers familiar with APIs. Documentation about the survey data itself (species, survey methodology, temporal and spatial coverage) is available on the dataset home page; users must rely on this external documentation to interpret results.

Suggestions for improvements (i) While the datasets are documented on the home page, endpoint-specific input/output information is not provided, and placeholder or missing values are not explained, limiting clarity for developers. The lack of documentation makes it difficult to construct correct queries or interpret responses reliably. The recommendation is to provide endpoint-specific input/output documentation, including sample requests and responses for each API, and indicate which endpoints are internal or experimental. (ii) No API-specific HTML, WSDL, or OpenAPI documentation describing inputs, outputs, or examples that exist beyond the Swagger list. The recommendation is that the added documentation is aimed at both humans and machines. (iii) While endpoints are listed via Swagger, those for internal use only are not distinguished. (iv) Recommendation is for a greater use of FAIR vocabularies and defined controlled codes (internal vocabularies) in the outputs, and to define the schema (JSON/XML) for the output data. (v) Add licence and version information to support reusability. (vi) The outputs should be provided in RDF with semantic annotation to allow full understandability of all the terms and values.

Stomach Content data REST API

The data on Stomach Content are provided via the ICES data portal, and we analysed the REST API, which provides programmatic and portal-based access to standardised fish predator-prey (stomach content) observations for use in diet studies, food-web analyses, and multi-species stock assessments in ICES regions. Data can be downloaded as a ZIP of CSV files containing File, Haul, Predator, and Prey information. The schema is defined as ICES DATSU (Data Submission Utility) dataset 157, with record types of FI (File_information), HH (Haul Information), PI (Predator Information), and PP (Prey Information). Public data are released under CC BY 4.0 per ICES Data Policy. The documented REST endpoints list: getFileInformation, getHaulInformation, getPredatorInformation, getPreyInformation, and Download. At the time of review, only the Download endpoint responded successfully; the others returned errors. If persistent, publish an uptime/status note or deprecate/replace the non-working endpoints.

Positives: The web inventory/download page and REST web services are straightforward, and the API page documents parameters with examples.

Suggestions for improvements (i) Fix the non-working endpoints; restore and monitor uptime for documented `get*` endpoints; add a status banner if outages persist. (ii) Provide small sample CSVs and cURL/Python/R snippets for common filters. (iii) Publish a compact codebook mapping columns to vocabularies (ISO-3166, EDMO, AphiaID, NODC prey codes). (iv) Add JSON options or a Parquet export for large-scale analysis. (v) Document rate limits, pagination (if any), and expected response sizes. (vi) The outputs should be provided in RDF with semantic annotation to allow full understandability of all the terms and values.

DOME SOAP API

DOME stores contaminants and biological effects monitoring data submitted under Environmental Reporting Format (ERF) v3.2. Submissions are validated via DATSU checks, assigned accession numbers, and – once accepted – become discoverable through the DOME portal and downloadable via SOAP web services and thematic views. Data are generally released under the ICES Data Policy with recommended citation. The DOME data portal is used by OSPAR, HELCOM, AMAP and ICES Expert Groups to provide managed collection, QA/validation, and programmatic access to these data.

Positives: Experienced API users can navigate the SOAP test pages. Newcomers benefit from copy-paste examples and parameter dictionaries. DATSU formats/checks are comprehensive, but they spread across resources, making it difficult to navigate. Portal pages describe scope, submission workflow (one data type per monitoring year per lab), citation, deadlines, and licence/policy. Thematic views help understand the structure before using APIs. SOAP WSDL exists for DOME web services, and functional endpoints are documented separately.

Suggestions for improvements (i) Outputs are in XML, which is machine-readable but not machine-understandable: Offer JSON (or better, JSON-LD) output (or a simple REST wrapper) alongside XML. (ii) Standardised formatting of data in the output could be improved (e.g. ISO for dates and countries, adding units). Related to this point: (iii) Link SOAP operation pages to ERF field definitions and ICES vocabularies, (iv) Publish a concise codebook for QA flags, missing values, and units. (v) Document pagination/throughput and recommended retry/backoff.

Continuous Underwater Noise service REST API

This service provides managed, standardised access to continuous low-frequency underwater noise data to support regional indicators and assessments (HELCOM and OSPAR), including discovery and download of submitted datasets and controlled, authenticated uploads. The portal hosts metadata, submission workflows, and web services. Public downloads are provided via two endpoints: `getListSubmissions` (lists submitted data files) and `DownloadFile/{FileID}` (retrieves a file by ID). Submission, screening, and pushing files into the database require authentication via a Token endpoint (JWT). The data format and checks are defined in the ICES Continuous Underwater Noise format (PDF).

Positives: The web services page enumerates endpoints and provides examples, along with documentation tailored for humans. It includes a description of the scope, programs, citations, and resources, and APIs are described on their webpage.

Suggestions for improvements (i) Adding JSON schemas and copy-paste code would improve onboarding. (ii) add OpenAPI for machine readability and better accessibility, and provide JSON/CSV small-subset API. (iii) Adding a developer-focused page would improve findability by this audience. (iv) register snapshot DOIs. (v) To improve the interoperability of the service and its outputs: reference standard CRS¹⁹ (EPSG:4326), link to station/area vocabularies, crosswalk to HELCOM/OSPAR indicator specifications, and embed a README and metadata in the output ZIP file.

ICES Catalogue

The ICES Metadata Catalogue is primarily a discovery service for metadata records about ICES datasets, services, and geospatial layers, enabling users to find and evaluate the availability, scope, and content of these records. The catalogue is based on GeoNetwork, an open-source metadata catalogue software. It hosts metadata created using international standards (ISO 19115/19139, INSPIRE) and includes spatial extent, temporal coverage, contacts, data formats, and links to access points when available. It provides a web search interface, which is its primary audience, and also offers machine-readable catalogue service endpoints (CSW, OAI-PMH) for harvesting and integration into other platforms. All metadata records are publicly available without authentication. ICES data managers create new metadata records.

Positives: The portal provides a good range of search possibilities presented in a very user-friendly way: keyword search, map-based spatial search, and filtering by categories. In addition to displaying records on the web page, metadata is also provided in ISO 19139 XML, which is machine-readable. Records have

¹⁹ WGS 84 Geographic Coordinate System

UUIDs, which are indexed and searchable, and the metadata are ISO/INSPIRE compliant, with some use of controlled vocabularies.

Suggestions for improvements (i) The CSW endpoint is not well-documented. (ii) Some fields in the search interface are highly technical and could be simplified for broader audiences. (iii) Metadata records generally reference the ICES Data Policy, but licence and citation fields are not always populated, and this should be improved (strictly speaking, no licence means no access). (iv) We suggest assigning DOIs to key datasets and registering the catalogue in DataCite/GEOSS. (v) Increase the use of controlled vocabularies (ICES, NERC, SeaDataNet). (vi) Ensure more provenance information is provided.

■ 2.2.3 Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI)

JSI has a single virtual service called IsoFoodTrack, which provides access to a dataset for food authenticity and traceability. IsoFoodTrack is aimed at researchers, the food industry, and policy makers. It provides a comprehensive database of isotopic and elemental composition, along with other data, and detailed metadata on commonly adulterated foods, aiding in the accurate verification of their authenticity and geographical origin. We tested this service without registration.

Positives: The home page is nice, clean, and easy to understand. Access to the different data is done with a single click. The data are displayed as nice tables and also via an easy-to-use map interface, whereby clicking on a point gives you the data for that point.

Suggestions for improvements (i) There is no documentation offered at all. It is therefore difficult to know what the history of these data is, who to contact with questions, what the columns in the tables are, and how to use the apparent filtering options on the table (we could not get it to work). We suggest that this documentation should be added. (ii) The tables cannot be exported: we suggest they should be provided in CSV and machine-understandable formats such JSON/JSON-LD. (We are told that work is ongoing on a REST service, and this may then be possible.) (iii) We suggest that greater interoperability will be achieved by using vocabularies for the parameters in the tables, a taxonomic backbone for the organism names, and ISO 8601 date format. (iv) No provenance information is provided: how were the data in the tables obtained, processed, and quality controlled? (v) The seafood database records altitudes greater than 0m: this is unlikely to be correct: perhaps a negative sign is missing?

2.3. Summary and Recommendations

The services tested offer access to a wide range of useful, curated, and authoritative data in the domain of marine science. All the services are open and free, web accessible, to humans and machines (developers), and are sufficiently well-presented that they do not take too long for a marine scientist/developer to be able to find, access, and use.

For all the web services aimed at developers, the main generally applicable criticisms that arose are

- **Improvements to documentation.**
 - Documentation should be written for the unknown person, who knows what they want to find, but does not know how the data is being served, is organised, annotated, described in the data management system, or even knows the full range of the data that can be served. Full explanation of all input parameters, range, and units, and the output formats, schemas, units, and parameters should be provided. Use-cases with examples of inputs and outputs should also be provided.
 - Documentation on the state of the various databases which the services were interrogating was also lacking or not so straightforward to find: information about the way the data were created, collected, or quality controlled, for example.
- **Greater use of controlled (FAIR) vocabularies** and semantics in the outputs is recommended, as well as the adoption of JSON-LD with defined schemas.
- **None of the web services offered much provenance** information. None of the outputs included basic execution data (when it was executed, version of the service used, what the inputs to the service were). Licence information for the returned data was generally lacking.

For all the services aimed at humans, we have provided some specific recommendations on the interface, behaviour, and documentation of each service. The main, generally applicable criticisms that arose are:

- **More interoperability of the outputs:** providing outputs in open, machine-readable and understandable formats, with greater use of vocabularies and URIs (where possible).
- **Search results should be downloadable.** For most of these services, the search results are a web page only, and we recommend that they are also exportable (in human and machine-readable formats).

A recommendation that applies to *all* the services tested

- **Professionals should write documentation.** Almost all of the services had documentation on the use of the service, and some also had documentation on the content of the data being served. However, for many of the services, we found it possible to easily misunderstand or overlook information due to the way the documentation was written or presented. There is never just one type of user with a single way of reading and understanding, and this is not adequately accommodated. Paying for professional documentation is understandably challenging for these organisations, which are typically underfunded, and it is rarely the case that such work is included in grant applications. Yet, because documentation is often a decisive factor in whether someone adopts a service, funding for professional documentation services should become more commonplace.

- Annex**

Table 1. List of the virtual services provided by VLIZ, JSI, and ICES

Name	Description	Landing page	Provider	Type	Audience*
WoRMS	APIs providing access to WoRM data	https://www.marinespecies.org/rest/	VLIZ	REST, SOAP	Machine, Human
WoRMS	Run a check on taxon names and obtain a set of WoRMS information for them	https://www.marinespecies.org/tutorial_taxonmatch.php	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
WoRMS	Browse a nested list of taxonomic names	https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=browser	VLIZ	Web page	Human
WRIMS	APIs providing access to WRIMS data	https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/aphia.php?p=rest , https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/aphia.php?p=soap	VLIZ	REST, SOAP	Machine, Human
WRIMS	Run a check on taxon names and obtain a set of WRIMS information for them	https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/aphia.php?p=match	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
Marine Regions	Find the webpages for regions based on coordinates, name, or MRGID	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=search	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
Marine Regions	Browse a nested list of marine regions	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=browse	VLIZ	Web page	Human
Marine Regions	APIs providing access to MarineRegions data	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=webservices	VLIZ	REST, SOAP	Machine, Human

Marine Regions	Linked Data Event Stream (LDES) exposing all gazetteer entries	https://www.marineregions.org/feed	VLIZ	LDES	Machine
Marine Regions	OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) services offering direct access to geographic data, maps, and metadata	https://www.marineregions.org/webservices.php	VLIZ	OGC	Machine
Marine Regions	GeoRSS feed reports all edits and updates of the Marine Gazetteer	Latest edits: https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=rss Latest records marked as checked https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=rss&type=check	VLIZ	GeoRSS	Machine
Marine Regions	R package using the OGC services	https://docs.ropensci.org/mregions2/	VLIZ	R scripts - OGC	Human
Marine Regions	Obtain information on maritime boundaries - string+coordinate search, map-interface search	https://www.marineregions.org/eezsearch.php , https://www.marineregions.org/eezmapper.php	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
Marine Regions	Download various maps	https://www.marineregions.org/maps.php	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
EurOBIS	Data download	https://eurobis.org/toolbox/en/download/occurrence/explore	VLIZ	Web page	Human
EurOBIS	Metadata catalogue search	https://www.eurobis.org/imi/s?module=dataset&extfrm=1	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
EurOBIS / EMODnet	Map viewer dataset search	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/	VLIZ / EMODnet	Web tool	Human

EurOBIS / EMODnet	Metadata catalogue search	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/emodnet/eng/catalog.search#/home	VLIZ / EMODnet	Web tool	Human
Marine Data Archive	Data archiving for long-term storage, sharing, publishing	https://mda.vliz.be/	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
Marine Info / Integrated Marine Information System	Data publishing via a metadata catalogue	https://marineinfo.org/submit-form	VLIZ	Web form	Human
Marine Info / Integrated Marine Information System	Dataset search via metadata catalogue	https://marineinfo.org/search	VLIZ	Web tool	Human
Marine Info / Integrated Marine Information System	Access dataset metadata via LOD publications	See https://marineinfo.org/products-and-services for details	VLIZ	LOD	Machine
IsoTrack	Web-based tool IsoFoodTrack on food isotopic and compositional data	http://isofoodtrack.ijs.si	JSI	Web tool	Machine, Human
DATRAS	API to search DATRAS, an online database of trawl surveys	https://datras.ices.dk/WebServices/Webservices.aspx	ICES	SOAP	Machine, Human
Data portal - Acoustic Data	API to search processed acoustic and biotic collected on acoustic trawl surveys in the Northeast Atlantic and Baltic seas	https://acoustic.ices.dk/services/swagger/index.html	ICES	REST	Machine, Human

Data portal - VME	API offering access to the Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem data of the ICES data portal	https://vme.ices.dk/webservices/ices.aspx , https://vme.ices.dk/API/GetPublicRecordsVMFDataSet	ICES	SOAP	Machine, Human
Data portal - Eggs and Larvae	API offering access to the data on Eggs and Larvae of the ICES data portal	https://eggsandlarvae.ices.dk/webservices	ICES	SOAP	Machine, Human
Data portal - Stomach Content	API to fetch Stomach Content Data from the ICES data portal	https://stomachdata.ices.dk/webservices	ICES	REST	Machine, Human
Data portal - DOME	API offering access to the chemical and biological data used by OSPAR, HELCOM, AMAP, and Expert groups, and validation of submissions and submission of new data	https://dome.ices.dk/api/swagger/index.html	ICES	REST	Machine, Human
Data portal - Continuous noise	API offering access to the continuous underwater noise of the ICES data portal	https://underwaternoise.ices.dk/continuous/webservices	ICES	REST, OData	Machine, Human
Assessment tools - stock information	API offering access to stock assessment data of the ICES data portal	https://sid.ices.dk/services/	ICES	REST	Machine, Human
ICES Metadata Catalogue	Browse the metadata catalogue of ICES data	https://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home	ICES	Web tool	Human

*Audience: "Machine" = developers, automated processes, "Human" = scientists and other data users

Table 2 . List of the e-services provided via ARIA

Name	Description	Landing page	Provider	Location
Bioinformatics	Genomics software, genome assembly, sequence databases	Not provided / Not available	ACOI	On-site
Bioinformatics	Genomics and transcriptomics software, genome assembly, sequence databases	Not provided / Not available	CIIMAR	On-site
Bioinformatics	Bioinformatics platform with genomics and transcriptomics software, genome assembly, sequence databases.	https://samba.nutrigrou-p-iats.org	CSIC-IATS-ANA	On-site and Remote
Bioinformatics	Fisheries assessment, catch estimation models, fisheries management, modeling and simulation of marine biological problems. Early disease detection in hatchery bivalve larvae using omics and AI.	Not provided / Not available	ECIMAT-UVIGO	On-site and Remote
Bioinformatics	Analysis of NGS data on HPC cluster "Zorbas", 3D image processing for Micro CT.	Not provided / Not available	HCMR-IMBBC	Remote
Bioinformatics	Platform/datacenter in Plouzané	Not provided / Not available	IFREMER-BMSA	Remote
Bioinformatics	Platform/datacenter in Plouzané	Not provided / Not available	IFREMER-FMSP	Remote and On-site

Bioinformatics	Online data access and analysis services. Numerous software tools for genomic and transcriptomic analysis, data analysis, statistics, mapping and imaging.	Not provided / Not available	IMR	On-site
Bioinformatics	Fish/aquatic animal imaging and data processing (appearance, shape, patterns, hyperspectral, behaviour). Image and CNN analysis. Behavioural metrics (speed, distribution, direction, interactions).	Not provided / Not available	JU-ICS	Remote
Bioinformatics	High Performance Computing and Bioinformatics platform, dedicated bioinformatics services and training. Strategies, resources, databases, scientific computational platforms for marine genomics.	Not provided / Not available	SZN	On-site and Remote
Bioinformatics	Genomics and transcriptomics software, genome assembly, sequence databases	Not provided / Not available	UMEA	On-site
Bioinformatics	16S rRNA gene sequencing analysis	https://www.disafa.unito.it/do/documenti.pl/S/how?id=1qg6	UNITO-Aqua	On-site and Remote
Bioinformatics	16S rRNA gene sequencing analysis	https://www.disafa.unito.it/do/documenti.pl/S/how?id=1qg6	UNITO-Insects	On-site and Remote

Dataset	Isofoodtrack database of data on food isotopes + web-based tool for managing the data on food isotopes	http://isofoodtrack.ijs.si	JSI	Remote Is also a virtual service (Table 2)
Dataset	Data from national monitoring activities from several sites in the Gulf of Bothnia both coastal and offshore, available in the databases dBotnia and BEDA covering 30 years of times series: hydrography, chemistry (nutrients, pH, alkalinity, DOC, humic substance, oxygen), biology (bacteria biomass and production, phytoplankton biomass and species composition as well as primary production, zooplankton composition, benthic fauna)	Not provided / Not available	UMEA	On-site However currently under review and not open for access
Spatial planning	Spatial planning service developed by Luke used in GIS-software to optimize the locations of fish farms in marine environments. The software considers different environmental, social and economic GIS-data criteria. The service has been provided to entrepreneurs, researchers, municipalities and government facilities.	https://www.luke.fi/en/services/the-finfarmgis-method-helps-to-assess-the-location-of-a-fish-farm	LUKE-FINFARMGIS	On-site
System Biology Modelling	Consulting in modeling and simulation of marine biological problems.	Not provided / Not available	ECIMAT-UVIGO	On-site and Remote